

THE EFFECT OF TOBACCO PRODUCTS ON THE INTERNAL ORGANS OF THE HUMAN BODY

*Assistant of the Department of propaedeutics of internal diseases of Bukhara
State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sina
dilrabo.halimova@mail.ru*

KHALIMOVA DILRABO JALILOVNA

*Deputy chief physician of the Bukhara City family polyclinic No. 2
umarovamaxfuza264@gmail.com*

UMAROVA MAXFUZA USMONOVNA

*Assistant of the Department of propaedeutics of internal diseases of Bukhara
State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sina
giza5552@gmail.com*

KODIROVA NARGIZAXON UMAROVNA

Annotation: In modern society, smoking is a common habit among various groups of the population, including women, adolescents and even children. According to statistics, there are about a billion people who regularly use tobacco in the world. Nicotine addiction is a serious danger to the human body. At the same time, awareness of the harm of tobacco is an effective motivation that helps to overcome cravings.

Keywords: tobacco, trophic tissues, smoking

The harm of smoking for the human body lies in its ability to stimulate the development of severe systemic diseases. Many of them are fatal. Briefly and eloquently about the harm that smoking causes to the body, according to medical statistics.

Approximately 5 million people die from tobacco every year in the world. Every day in Russia alone, nicotine takes about 1 thousand lives. Approximately 90% of lung cancer deaths are caused by tobacco use. It is proved that the life of a person with nicotine addiction is 9 years shorter than that of his non-smoking peer.

Lung cancer in people who use tobacco is 10 times more common. Regular ingestion of saliva with nicotine breakdown products contributes to the development of cancer of the oral cavity, esophagus, stomach and duodenum. In the lungs of a person with nicotine addiction, resins that contribute to the development of diseases of the respiratory system, including fatal ones, settle and accumulate.

Smoking causes enormous harm to the heart and blood vessels. After one cigarette, blood pressure rises, the risk of thrombosis and blockage of the arteries increases. The pulse of a person who uses tobacco is 15,000 heartbeats per day more often than that of a non-smoker. Thus, the load on his heart is about 20% higher than normal. Vasoconstriction causes oxygen starvation of tissues — hypoxia.

An increase in the blood of a smoker of catecholamine's contributes to an increase in the concentration of lipids and the development of atherosclerosis, hypertension and fatty degeneration of the heart. Various disorders of the sexual sphere caused by narrowing of the vessels of the pelvis occur 3 times more often in smokers than in non-smokers. 20,000 lower limb amputations are performed annually due to obliterating endarteritis. The disease develops as a result of a violation of the due to insufficient blood supply caused by tobacco use.

Recent research data prove a link between nicotine addiction and blindness. Dystrophy of the retina and the vascular membrane of the eye due to insufficient blood supply, as well as the destructive effect of poisons on the optic nerve cause the harm of smoking to the visual apparatus.

Along with this, nicotine has a negative effect on the hearing aid. The released toxic substances have a destructive effect on the innervation of the internal structures of the ear. Due to the death of sensitive receptors, sleep problems arise, the sense of smell and taste sensations are dulled.

Nicotine addiction depletes the nervous system and slows down brain activity. The reactions of a smoking person slow down, intelligence decreases.

Tobacco use contributes to a decrease in the motor function of the stomach and intestines, negatively affects the condition and functional activity of the liver.

Mortality from diseases of the digestive system — stomach ulcers and duodenal ulcers — in smokers is 3.5 times higher than in non-smokers.

Nicotine negatively affects the appearance, causing deterioration of the skin, darkening of teeth and an unpleasant smell. It is proved that tobacco use contributes to accelerated biological aging — the functional indicators of the body do not correspond to age.

Smoking causes great harm to the body of a pregnant woman and fetus. Chronic hypoxia causes delays in its development and poses a threat of miscarriage. Children of mothers who smoke during pregnancy are often born prematurely. They often have signs of hypotrophy and immaturity, often get sick and lag behind their peers in development.

Besides the fact that smoking is harmful to health, it is the cause of many fires, often leading to disability or death.

Smoking harms not only the health of the smoker, but also his family and employees. People who are constantly nearby regularly inhale smoke. Its excess indoors can cause dizziness, nausea and vomiting, cough, irritation of the mucous membranes of the eyes and throat, allergy attacks. In non-smokers, tobacco smoke contributes to the development of the same diseases as in smokers.

The destructive effect of smoking on the body of any person is its ability to cause:

- various types of cancer;
- myocardial infarction;
- stroke;
- pulmonary thromboembolism;
- atherosclerosis;
- blindness;
- deafness;
- obliterating endarteritis;
- impotence and frigidity;

- infertility;
- emphysema of the lungs;
- pneumonia;
- chronic bronchitis;
- destruction of tooth enamel;
- gastrointestinal diseases;
- congenital deformities;
- lag in development;
- early mortality.

The harm of smoking to the body of passive smokers is confirmed by medical statistics: about 600 thousand people die in the world every year, 300 thousand of whom are children. These and other scientific data became the foundation for the adoption of a law banning smoking in public places.

Getting rid of smoking is simple. To do this, you just need to understand that cigarettes are not able to bring anything positive to life. Having a strong desire to change your own life, improve your appearance, and health is an excellent reason to start fighting an existing bad habit. Quite often, this motivation is quite enough for someone who has a really strong desire to get rid of smoking. Therefore, answering the question of how to get rid of smoking forever, first of all you need to form your own motivation. After all, it should act not only in the first days of quitting smoking, but also in the future, guaranteeing a healthy, long, full of all kinds of bright moments of life. All this will be the best reward for experiencing nicotine withdrawal.

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